

Investigation of modelling-dependent system reliability for open steel-concrete composite girder bridges

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ABSTRACT

The Eurocode EN 1990 provides only limited guidance on the structural models to be used by engineers for the design of bridges, and does not specify model-dependent partial safety factors for global structural design. This implies uniformly applicable partial safety factors and therefore a model-independent system reliability. The aim of this study is to investigate the validity of this statement and present methods for quantifying a model-dependent system reliability. These methods will be demonstrated for an open girder composite bridge by comparing two bridge modelling approaches: a grillage model where the section properties of equivalent composite girders are assigned to orthogonally aligned beam elements and a slab-beam model that uses shell elements to represent the concrete slab and beam elements to represent the steel girders.

Differences in the distribution of the action effects for traffic loads between both modelling approaches are shown in a comparison of the sagging moment for open composite girder bridges with reasonable dimensions for three different load cases and are quantified by the variable θ_E . An investigation of the probabilistic description of the resistance function for both modelling approaches by scattering the input parameters and including a resistance model uncertainty factor shows that the proposed design values according to the Eurocodes align well with the derived probabilistic description of both resistance functions.

By combining the findings of the investigations, a procedure is presented for evaluating the system reliability by including the distribution of the resistance side and an action-sided distribution based on the previous results and values from literature. The factor θ_δ required to adjust the action effects of the grillage model in order to reach the same system reliability as the slab-beam model, varies within a similar – but not equivalent – range as the model uncertainty on the action side θ_E . This factor θ_δ could thereby be used in further investigations to derive a correction factor between the two modelling approaches.

Keywords: bridge modelling, composite bridge, model uncertainty, reliability analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

Eurocode EN 1990 (1) gives structural engineers the freedom to choose “appropriate structural models” as long as the “structural models [are] based on established engineering theory and practice.” This practice is used, for example, in the design of bridges and allows engineers to use a structural model rather freely to determine the action effects and perform design checks.

The selection of the structural model also affects the description of the resistance functions. For instance, using structural models based on beam elements will lead to a cross-sectional design evaluation, whereas the use of more sophisticated 2D or 3D finite element models may necessitate a stress or strain-based design approach at a finite element-based level.

The classical approach to verify a structure is by using the semi-probabilistic design approach according to EN 1990 (1), where the probability of failure p_f quantified by the reliability index β (see

Eq. (1)) for the action and resistance side is partitioned using the sensitivity factors α_E and α_R (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Semi-probabilistic design concept of Eurocode 1990, Annex C (1)

$$\beta = -\Phi^{-1}(p_f) \quad (1)$$

The design value of the resistance R_d is calibrated based on the probabilistic distribution of the resistance function and the cumulative probability of the standard normal distribution at a value of $\alpha_R \cdot \beta$ (see Eq. (2)). The reliability index proposed by EN 1990 (1) is $\beta = 3.8$, with sensitivity factors of $\alpha_R = -0.8$ and $\alpha_E = 0.7$.

$$P(R \leq R_d) = \Phi(\alpha_R \cdot \beta) \quad (2)$$

To reach the design value of the resistance R_d and of the action effects E_d , the nominal results are scaled by so-called partial safety factors γ_M and γ_F . While these partial safety factors take into account the scatter and the uncertainty of the input parameters, there does not appear to be any differentiation between different modelling approaches. To account for this, the Eurocode for design assisted by finite element analysis of steel structures prEN 1993-1-14 (2) proposes a procedure to calibrate a partial safety factor γ_{FE} considering the influence of the modelling uncertainty on the action and resistance side resulting from the finite element model. However, there is still a lack of clear values for model-dependent partial safety factors for global bridge designs or a procedure explaining how they could be computed. Therefore, this study aims to present an approach to evaluate the model uncertainty between two modelling methods, exemplified by a global design check for an open girder composite bridge for highway traffic loads.

First, this paper presents two accepted modelling approaches for the investigation of global action effects in composite bridges. Then, it compares the differences in the action effects due to traffic loads and in the description of the resistance functions between the two models. Finally, this paper presents an approach that combines uncertainties on the action and resistance side, enabling the quantification in the system reliability of the structural models.

2 BRIDGE MODELLING

2.1 Investigated bridge models

This paper presents a general approach to investigating model-dependent uncertainties, which will be presented for a double span open twin-girder composite bridge as seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the investigate composite bridge in transverse (left) and longitudinal direction (right)

The structural models which will be compared are a grillage model and a more advanced slab-beam model. The general modelling approaches of both models are explained in the subsequent chapters.

2.2 Software used for bridge modelling

The commercial software SOFiSTiK (3) is used for the investigation of the bridge action effects. The structural analysis software SOFiSTiK offers advantages over other software due to its ability to generate parametric bridge models and automate the extraction and post-processing of results, making its application beneficial for this study.

2.3 Grillage model

The grillage model represents the bridge structure by orthogonally aligning beam elements in longitudinal and transverse direction (see Fig. 3). Stiffness components of the bridge structure are then assigned to the beam elements in accordance to propositions from the literature (4) and (5).

The grillage model is highly applicable due to its easy and understandable development, fast computation and ability to use the resulting forces and deformations in a beam-like manner. This allows to verify the section using resistance functions derived for beam-like structures.

While the grillage model leads to general good results for the design in longitudinal direction, its usage for local design checks is not recommended. The main girders spanning in longitudinal direction represent the composite girder consisting of the properties of the steel girder and a proportion of the concrete slab while the torsional stiffness is assigned to a central beam. The assigned stiffness of the transverse beams represents the concrete deck while the influence of the cross-bracings on the stiffness is neglected as deemed conservative (5). The assigned effective width of the concrete deck considering the shear lag effect is determined using the equations from EN 1994-2 (6). In the vicinity of 15 % of the adjacent spans the concrete over the support is assumed to be cracked, thus reducing the bending stiffness of the main girder over the support.

Fig. 3. Grillage model in SOFiSTiK

Fig. 4. Slab-beam model in SOFiSTiK

2.4 Slab-beam model

The second proposed model represents the concrete deck by shell elements (see Fig. 4), while the steel girders are represented by longitudinal beam elements having assigned only the steel girder cross-section components (see Fig. 5). To maintain consistency with the assumption of a rigid connection between the steel girder and the concrete deck in the grillage model, a rigid connection

has been applied between the concrete slab and the steel girders. This modelling approach is based on an investigation of different approaches from (7) which showed good agreement compared with the behaviour of tested composite girders.

Fig. 5. General configuration of slab-beam model, based on (7)

As previously stated for the grillage model, the concrete is assumed to be cracked in a vicinity of 15 % of the adjacent span over the support in the longitudinal direction while remaining uncracked in the transverse direction. Consequently, the concrete shell elements are represented by a reduced stiffness in the longitudinal direction over the support region, depending on the reinforcement ratio ρ . Transverse steel girders acting as cross-bracing elements are considered in this modelling approach by representing them using beam elements. However, a sensitivity analysis showed that their inclusion does not significantly affect the resulting action effects. The shear modulus of the concrete is determined according to (8).

2.5 Range of bridge dimensions

The bridges' dimensions were selected according to (9) and supplemented with appropriate values where additional information was necessary. The corresponding dimensions and input parameters are depicted in *Table 1* according to the notation of *Fig. 2*.

Table 1. Range of geometric bridge dimensions

Variable	Min	Max	Unit	Variable	Min	Max	Unit
B	8	14	[m]	t_{fb}	20	70	[mm]
ρ	1	10	[%]	B_{fb}	400	1200	[mm]
t_c	200	500	[mm]	t_w	10	20	[mm]
e_B/B	0.3	0.7	[-]	h_w/L_1	1/30	1/15	[-]
t_{ft}	15	50	[mm]	L_1	20	60	[m]
B_{ft}	300	1000	[mm]	L_2/L_1	0.8	1.0	[-]

3 INVESTIGATION OF ACTION EFFECTS

The difference in the action effects between the model approaches is investigated by comparing the sagging moment in the greater span L_1 for different loading scenarios (see *Fig. 6*) based on the dimensions from *Table 1*. These load cases are considered a simplified representation of highway traffic loads.

Fig. 6: Investigated load cases

In order to compare the sagging moment between the two model approaches, the action effects from the slab-beam bridge model are transformed into a bending moment $M_{Comp,S}$ acting on a composite girder, corresponding to the bending moment of the grillage model $M_{Comp,G}$. The bending moment of the steel girder M_a , the concrete slab M_c and the corresponding acting normal forces N_a and N_c are translated into $M_{Comp,S}$ using *Eq. (3)*.

$$M_{Comp,S} = M_a + M_c + N_a \cdot a_a + N_c \cdot a_c \quad (3)$$

Where a_a and a_c correspond to the distance between the centroid of the steel girder (and the concrete slab respectively) and the centroid of the composite cross-section. The action effects of the concrete slab M_c and N_c are determined by integrating the local shell forces over the width of the equivalent concrete slab by an in-built function of SOFiSTiK. An alternative approach would be to convert the action effects from the composite section resulting from the grillage model into forces acting purely on the steel girder. The ratio between the action effects from the slab-beam model and the grillage model are described using the variable θ_E (see *Eq. (4)*).

$$\theta_E = \frac{M_{Comp,S}}{M_{Comp,G}} \quad (4)$$

For a total of 200 different bridge configurations, the values for θ_E are depicted in *Fig. 7* for the three previously illustrated load cases (*Fig. 6*), while the probabilistic parameters of the fitted distributions for θ_E can be found in *Table 4*.

Fig. 7: Histograms and fitted distributions for θ_E for investigated load cases

The results show that there is an overall agreement of the sagging moment between the grillage model and the slab-beam model. The action effects of the grillage model tend to underpredict the bending moment for the line load and overpredict it for the uniformed distributed load and the point load when compared to the slab-beam model.

4 RESISTANCE FUNCTIONS

This chapter dedicates itself to the investigation of the probabilistic description of the resistance function both for the composite girder as well as for the steel girder which are later required to perform a full-probabilistic analysis. The probabilistic distribution of the resistance functions can be evaluated by determining the resistance based on a probabilistic description of the geometry, material and the accuracy of the resistance model. By comparing the design values of the distribution of the resistance function using the concept of EN 1990 (1) (see *Eq. (2)*) with the design values proposed by the

Eurocode, an assessment can be made regarding the current applicability of the partial safety factors in use.

4.1 Description of resistance functions

The composite girder from the grillage model is loaded in pure bending, while the action effects of the slab-beam model are already subdivided into forces acting on the concrete slab and forces acting on the steel girder. Therefore, the resistance function differs between both modelling approaches. Whereas for the grillage model the bending resistance is derived for a composite section under positive bending moment, for the slab-beam model the steel girder resistance is investigated under combined bending and normal force.

Although the resistance classification depends on the steel classifications according to EN 1993-1-1 (10), the girder resistance in this study will nonetheless be determined elastically (class 3 or 4). The resistance function of the composite girder enables a direct redistribution of the internal forces to achieve a full plastic resistance. However, this is not possible for the pure steel girder as the plastic redistribution must already occur during the calculation of the action effects, necessitating a non-linear analysis of the structural model. The elastic resistance of the section is therefore determined using a stress-based approach, where failure occurs when the stress reaches the material strength at one point.

In the case of the composite section, the cross-sectional values were evaluated by dividing the cross-sectional values of the concrete by the modular ratio $n = E_a/E_c$ (11). As this study investigates action effects induced by traffic loads, long-term effects due to creep and shrinkage do not need to be considered. In the case of cross-section class 4, the method of effective width was implemented according to EN 1993-1-5 (12). The partial safety factor for the steel resistance is set to $\gamma_{M0} = 1.00$ according to EN 1993-2 (13) and to $\gamma_c = 1.5$ for concrete according to EN 1992-1-1 (14).

4.2 Material and geometric parameters

The material classes of concrete and steel have been set to C35/45 and S355, so that the nominal values of the concrete and steel follow the proposals of the Eurocodes. The probabilistic characteristics of the material and geometric parameters are listed in *Table 2*.

Table 2: Probabilistic properties of material and geometry

Variable name	Variable	Mean	C.o.V.	Design values	Source
Concrete compression strength	f_c	$f_{c,nom} + 8 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$\frac{8 \text{ N/mm}^2/1.64}{f_{c,nom} + 8 \text{ N/mm}^2}$	$f_{c,nom}/\gamma_c$	(14)
Modulus of elasticity concrete	E_c	$1.0 \cdot E_{c,nom}$	15 %	$E_{c,nom}$	(15)
Yield strength steel	f_y	$1.2 \cdot f_{y,nom}$	5.0 %	$f_{y,nom}/\gamma_{M0}$	(10)
Modulus of elasticity steel	E_a	$210'000 \text{ N/mm}^2$	3.0 %	E_a	(10)
Depth & width of steel plates	h_a, b_a	$1.0 \cdot \{h_a, b_a\}$	0.9 %	h_a, b_a	(10)
Thickness of steel plates	t_a	$0.99 \cdot t_a$	2.5 %	t_a	(10)
Dimensions of concrete slab	X	$1.003 \cdot X_{nom}$	$\frac{4 [\text{mm}] + 0.6 \cdot X_{nom}}{1.003 \cdot X_{nom}}$	X_{nom}	(15)

4.3 Model uncertainty of the bending resistance

The model uncertainty on the resistance side θ_R represents the deviation of the applied analytical formulations from the effective resistance of the investigated section. Only few studies or suggested values were found for the resistance model uncertainty for plated steel and composite girders subjected to bending. Therefore, a systematic evaluation of the model uncertainty factor for plated steel girders is recommended for further works. The proposed values from literature are listed in *Table 3*.

Table 3: Proposed literature values for steel resistance model uncertainty θ_R

Distribution	Mean	C.o.V.	Source	Additional information
LN	1.0	5 %	(15)	Steel bending and/or shear
N	1.1	6.3 %	(16)	Steel; unspecified failure mode
LN	1.15	5 %	(17)	Steel; unspecified failure mode

As most of these propositions increase the effective resistance of the section ($\theta_R > 1.0$), the model uncertainty proposed by the JSCC (15) is chosen as a conservative assumption.

4.4 Reliability evaluation on resistance side

To determine the design resistance of the composite girder $M_{Rd,SIM}$ based on the probabilistic resistance distribution, the value can be calculated using the mean value $M_{Rm,SIM}$ and the coefficient of variation $v_{R,SIM}$ based on the distribution of the resistance function as shown in Fig. 8 (left).

In the case of the resistance function of the steel girder, the 1-dimensional resistance parameter R is introduced. This parameter lies on an axis with a slope of $\alpha = N/M$, based on the action effects of the steel girder N_a and M_a . Both the extracted design value for the resistance function $R_{d,SIM}$ and the Eurocode design resistance $R_{d,EC}$ can be determined based on values that satisfy the condition $N_R/M_R = \alpha$ (Fig. 8 right).

Fig. 8. Concept for quantification of design resistance for normal distributed resistance functions in 1D (left) and 2D (right)

While the resistance distribution of the composite girder is independent on the loading condition, the pair of M and N acting on the steel girder affects the description – and thus the probabilistic distribution – of the resistance function. The distribution of the resistance function of the steel girder is therefore determined for each of the three load cases depicted in Fig. 6. The resulting ratios between $R_{d,SIM}$ and $R_{d,EC}$ for the 200 simulated bridge configurations and the probabilistic properties according to Table 2 and Table 3 are presented in Fig. 9. For the sake of simplicity, the bending moment resistance M_R will be denoted by the variable R in the following figures and discussions.

The results indicate that the design resistance $R_{d,SIM}$ for a pure steel girder agree with the values proposed by the Eurocode within minor differences. There appear to be only minimal differences between the loading conditions although the values of $\alpha = N/M$ do change.

When evaluating the accuracy of the Eurocode design concept for the composite girder, it is important to note that while the resistance function agrees fairly well with the values suggested by the Eurocodes, there is a greater scatter with a mean value around $R_{d,SIM}/R_{d,EC} \approx 1.0$. In some configurations, the stress in the concrete becomes governing for the Eurocode design case, whereas the yield stress of the steel is reached first for the simulated resistances. This difference in the failure modes results in a ratio $R_{d,SIM}/R_{d,EC}$ significantly greater than 1.0.

Fig. 9: Ratio between $R_{d,SIM}$ and $R_{d,EC}$ for grillage and slab-beam model

5 EVALUATION OF SYSTEM RELIABILITY

After investigating the differences in the description of the action effects and the resistance for both modelling approaches separately in the previous chapters, this chapter focuses on the model-dependent reliability of the full limit state, which consists of both the action and resistance side. While the resistance functions for the 200 simulated bridges presented previously have already been determined, it is necessary to clarify an approach for considering a probabilistic distribution of the action effects.

Previous studies (e.g. (18)) investigating the distribution of action effects for axle load sequences based on traffic simulations have shown that an extreme value distribution is reasonable to represent the distribution of traffic load action effects. Instead of performing similar calculations to determine the distribution of load effects due to an axle load sequence for each of the 200 simulated bridges, a more general approach is adopted. The design value of the action effects M_{Ed} or E_d respectively is anchored at the quantile corresponding to a value of $\alpha_E \cdot \beta$ in the standard normal distributed space, thus fulfilling the requirements of the semi-probabilistic design concept by the designer. Assuming a constant coefficient of variation for the traffic action effects of $v = 10\%$, as similar values have been derived in real measurements (19), the parameters of the probabilistic extreme value distribution can be back calculated. To represent the extreme value distribution, a right-tailed Gumbel distribution is adopted. This allows the system reliability $\beta_{System,S}$ for the slab-beam model to be determined by applying the linear Hasofer-Lind algorithm (20). The differences with respect to the system reliability of the grillage model are then quantified by applying the procedure shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Conceptual quantification of model-dependent differences of the system reliability

The variable δ_S (see Eq. (5)) describes the ratio between the mean value of the action effects of the slab-beam model E_m and the action effects of the slab-beam model E_{calc} from the three load cases.

$$\delta_S = \frac{E_m}{E_{\text{calc}}} \quad (5)$$

The mean value of the distribution of the action effects for the grillage model is then given by multiplying the action effects from the grillage model $M_{\text{Comp,G}}$ with δ_S . As the derived system reliability $\beta_{\text{Syst,G}}$ does not necessary coincide with $\beta_{\text{Syst,S}}$, the action effects of the grillage model are multiplied by an additional factor θ_δ to reach the same reliability index as determined for the slab-beam model.

Fig. 11: θ_δ and θ_E for investigated load cases

A comparison between θ_δ and θ_E shows the difference between adapting the action effects to achieve uniform action effects (θ_E) and adapting the action effects to reach a uniformed system reliability (θ_δ). In this case, the probabilistic distributions of θ_δ for the three load cases show less divergence from each other compared to the distributions of θ_E (see Table 4 and Fig. 11).

Table 4: Probabilistic distribution of θ_δ and θ_E for investigated load cases

Load case	Distr.	θ_δ			θ_E		
		μ	σ	C.o.V.	μ	σ	C.o.V.
UDL	LN	1.045	0.047	0.045	1.058	0.024	0.023
Line load	LN	0.977	0.054	0.055	0.988	0.050	0.051
Point load	LN	1.050	0.045	0.043	1.076	0.053	0.049

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This study presents a framework for an investigation of the full reliability analysis for two different structural modelling approaches for open girder composite bridges. Rather than comparing the action effects and the resistances independently and deriving independent correction factors, an approach is presented that identifies the factors required to achieve a uniform system reliability for both modelling approaches. Despite some assumptions and simplifications by considering only pure elastic failure mode in the steel section and representing the traffic action effects in a simplified manner, the results show that there exist systematic differences between a full probabilistic analysis and an analysis based on a semi-probabilistic concept.

This study highlights some further investigations not covered in this article that could help to provide more accurate results: a systematic investigation of the model uncertainty for the resistance model for plated structures θ_R , the inclusion of multiple failure modes within the same limit state function and the representation of action effects in a more realistic way using simulation-based axle load sequences.

REFERENCES

1. **prEN 1990:2019.** *Eurocode - Basis of structural and geotechnical design.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2019.
2. **prEN 1993-1-14.** *Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-14: Design assisted by finite element analysis.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2022.
3. **SOFiSTiK AG.** *SOFiSTiK Manual.* Nuremberg, Germany : SOFiSTiK AG, 2023.
4. **Unterweger, Harald.** *Globale Systemberechnung von Stahl- und Verbundbrücken; Modellbildung und Leistungsfähigkeit verbesserter einfacher Stabmodelle.* Graz : Technische Universität Graz, 2007.
5. **Hambly, E.C.** *Bridge Deck Behaviour - Second Edition.* London : Taylor & Francis, 1976.
6. **EN 1994-2:2005.** *Eurocode 4 - Design of composite steel and concrete structures - Part 2: General rules and rules for bridges; German version EN 1994-2:2005 + AC:2008.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2005.
7. **Chung, Wonseok and Sotelino, Elisa D.** Three-dimensional finite element modeling of composite girder bridges. *Engineering Structures.* 2006, pp. 63-71.
8. **Vayas, Ioannis and Iliopoulos, Aristidis.** *Design of Steel-Concrete Composite Bridges to Eurocodes.* Boca Raton : CRC Press, 2014.
9. **Lebet, Jean-Paul and Hirt, Manfred A.** *Steel bridges; Conceptual and structural Design of Steel and Steel-Concrete Composite Bridges.* Lausanne, Boca Raton : EPFL Press, CRC press, 2009.
10. **prEN 1993-1-1:2020.** *Eurocode 3 - Design of steel structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2021.
11. **Dujmovic, Darko, Androic, Boris and Lukacevic, Ivan.** *Composite Structures according to Eurocode 4 - Worked Examples.* Berlin, Germany : Ernst & Sohn, 2015.
12. **prEN 1993-1-5.** *Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-5: Plated structural elements.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2020.
13. **EN 1993-2:2006.** *Eurocode 3 - Design of steel structures - Part 2: Steel Bridges; German version EN 1993-2:2006 + AC:2009.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2010.
14. **EN 1992-1-1:2004.** *Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings; German version EN 1992-1-1:2004 + AC:2010.* Brussels : CEN - European Committee for Standardization, 2011.
15. **Joint Committee on Structural Safety .** *Probabilistic Model Code Part 3.* 2000.
16. **Gulvanessian, Haig and Holicky, Milan.** Reliability based calibration of Eurocodes considering a steel member. *JCSS Workshop on Reliability Based Code Calibration.* 2002.
17. **Sykora, Miroslav.** Comparison of load combination models for probabilistic calibrations. *Applications of Statistics and Probability in Civil Engineering.* 2011.
18. **Treacy, Mark A., Brühwiler, Eugen and Caprani, Colin C.** Monitoring of traffic action local effects in highway bridge deck slabs and the influence of measurement duration on extreme value estimates. *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering.* 2014.
19. **Kozikowski, Marek.** *WIM based live load model for bridge reliability.* Lincoln, NE : University of Nebraska, 2009.
20. **Melchers, Robert E. and Beck, André T.** *Structural Reliability Analysis and Prediction, Third Edition.* Hoboken, NJ : Wiley, 2018.